

```
1 version: '3.8'
2
3 services:
4   president-api:
5     build: .
6     ports:
7       - "8000:8000"
8     environment:
9       - PYTHONUNBUFFERED=1
10    volumes:
11      - ./president_v1_3.py:/app/president_v1_3.py
12    command: uvicorn president_v1_3:app --host 0.0.0.0 --port 8000 --reload
13    restart: unless-stopped
14
15 # base de données pour la persistance
16 postgres:
17   image: postgres:15
18   environment:
19     POSTGRES_DB: president_db
20     POSTGRES_USER: president_user
21     POSTGRES_PASSWORD: president_pass
22   volumes:
23     - postgres_data:/var/lib/postgresql/data
24   ports:
25     - "5432:5432"
26
27 volumes:
28   postgres_data:
```